

A reproducibility study: Contrastive Learning with Hard Negative Entities for Entity Set Expansion

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1 INTRODUCTION

In Semantic Systems, it often becomes necessary to expand a semantic class when new data provides additional potential entities. A problem for this so-called Entity Set Expansion (ESE) lies in the fact that different semantic classes are often characterized by similar patterns, such that new entities may wrongly be attributed to a given class. Since such Hard Negative Entities can drastically harm a model's performance (Semantic Drift), the article under investigation tries to reduce the pitfall by making use of a Contrastive Learning approach in order to construct more suitable semantic boundaries between different classes [1].

With the goal being to reproduce the above-mentioned studies results', this paper aims to provide insights about the reliability and availability of resources in order to do so. While the outcomes are critically limited due to a lack of computational resources, the results approximate those of the original study, indicating that with better hardware similar/equal results can be expected.

In the following, this study is split into two main parts. First, the experimental setup will be described while the second part will compare the results of both, the original and the reproduced study.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The authors assess the question at hand with the experiment design highlighted in Figure 1. Hereby, the model architecture for ESE constitutes the independent variable, where the baseline condition is the set of models without Contrastive Learning (CL): The respective models are drawn from different papers, namely Egoset [3], SetExpan [5], SetExpander [2], CaSE [6], CGExpan [7], and SynSetExpan [4]. The CL-models, ProbExpan and ProbExpan-CN, serve as the treatment condition and both were created by the authors themselves. The dependent variable of the study is the performance of the respective models, where the paper mainly focusses on the best performing model in the baseline and treatment group. The evaluation of each method is based on the Mean Average Precision (MAP@K) metric, which measures the average precision across all semantic classes in the datasets, at various top-K positions where choice of k is based on previous works [4], [7]. MAP provides a comprehensive evaluation of the ranked list of expanded entities belonging to the same semantic class and hence provides a suited measure whether the introduction of CL-approaches actually help against Hard Negative Entities.

In order to improve the robustness of the study, the authors also chose to compare the results across three datasets (Wiki, APR, SE2 [4]), which show different characteristics regarding their number of semantic classes and seed entities of a semantic class. Naturally, the comparison is made for each dataset separately.

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Fig. 1. The illustrated experiment design

2.1 Implementation

For implementing the above described procedure, the authors needed to train many models, which was done in the following four phases:

- (1) Multiple models were trained in parallel in a masked entity prediction task
- (2) The top K models were selected based on an algorithm which takes the probabilistic representation of seed entities into account
- (3) training multiple models in parallel with contrastive loss and masked entity prediction loss
- (4) selecting and ensembling models in the same way as in phase 2

The authors state that the framework is efficient as bottom layers of the encoder are frozen, all models are trained in parallel, and the predicted entity distributions are calculated and saved for easy retrieval during model selection and ensemble. See [Figure 2](#) for an overview of their proposed method, where the authors:

- (1) Joint training of an entity representation model f using both an entity prediction task and a contrastive learning task to obtain clearer semantic boundaries.
- (2) Use of multiple pre-trained entity representation models with a model selection and ensemble mechanism to reduce the impact of randomness.
- (3) Utilization of two algorithms (window-search and entity re-ranking) to search and sort entities based on their probabilistic representation similarity.

See [subsection 3.2](#) for the reproduction of the four implementation phases and the computation of the results.

2.2 Evaluation Studies

The authors conducted three different studies, which will be briefly summarized.

Parameter Study The paper proposes to automatically select negative entities using a pre-defined interval (L_{neg} , U_{neg}) and manually adjust L_{neg} to be slightly larger than the size of positive entities. However, the performance of the proposed ProbExpan model is insensitive to the values of (L_{neg} and U_{neg}) due to the design of other structures and training strategy. This is proven theoretically through the adaptivity of the contrastive loss and empirically through experiments where changes in the values of (L_{neg} and U_{neg}) resulted in only slight changes to the model performance.

Ablation Studies The study was conducted to analyze the proposed method of CGExpan on Entity Set Expansion (ESE) using a series of ablation experiments. The variants of ProbExpan were compared with CGExpan-NoCN, which is

Fig. 2. Figure 2 from Li et al.[1], Illustration of the proposed methods

a traditional pre-trained language model. The variants of ProbExpan included: ProbExpan-NoCLEN without contrastive learning and model selection/ensemble, ProbExpan-NoEN without model selection/ensemble, and ProbExpan-NoCL without contrastive learning. The results were analyzed to determine the impact of entity-level masked language models, contrastive learning, and model selection/ensemble strategies on ESE performance. The validity of the equation used for evaluating the model was also analyzed.

Case Studies The study compares the performance of various models of ProbExpan in entity expansion. It focuses on using contrastive learning to differentiate between positive and negative samples in the semantic space, leading to clearer semantic class boundaries. It also employs a model selection and ensemble mechanism to improve results, as seen in the comparison between ProbExpan-NoEN and ProbExpan. The effectiveness of these strategies is demonstrated through results obtained from several queries belonging to different semantic classes, as shown in Figure 5. Their results showed that ProbExpan (CL) was able to outperform ProbExpan-NoCLEN (\neg CL), and the use of contrastive learning and the model selection mechanism led to improvement in entity expansion.

3 RESULTS

First we quickly summarize the main findings and results of Li et al, secondly we go into detail about the reproduction of the results.

3.1 Li et al. Results

The results show that the proposed method, ProbExpan, outperforms all the baselines, including the current state-of-the-art methods, on the three datasets. The proposed method also demonstrates stable performance compared to the fluctuating performance of existing methods. Additionally, the performance improvement of ProbExpan-CN compared to ProbExpan suggests that the proposed method can be easily combined with other ESE methods.

See Table 1 for their results on *ProbExpan No-CL* and *ProbExpan + CL*, more results can be found in section 4 of their work [1]. As we also only looked at these two (because of computational reasons, see *Limitations*), we exclude their results on CGExpan-NoCN, ProbExpan-NoCLEN, ProbExpan-NoEN.

Wiki-Data	MAP@10	MAP@20	MAP@50	MAP@100
ProbExpan No-CL	0.991	0.980	0.917	-
ProbExpan + CL	0.995	0.982	0.962	-

Table 1. Results (Table 3) from Li et al., for more see their work, section 4 [1].

3.2 Reproduction

Here want to detail our approach to reproduce the results, highlight challenges and finally present our obtained results. The respective code, including the two models can be found on GitHub ¹.

Setup There is a linked GitHub repository ² which we cloned. After this, we tried to find the three different datasets through references papers and found the Wiki and APR data ³. The third data set difficult to find, but due to computational restrictions we stuck to the wiki data (see *Limiations* for more).

Further, the APR data set can not be used in the state it is in after the download. It comes in a "raw" format, while the source code from the repository requires the data to be in a JSON-format (wiki data is in JSON-format). There are also no scripts or functions described which enable the conversion of data from raw format into JSON-format. Furthermore, implementing the mapping on our own was not feasible. There are two main dependencies: CUDA and the the transformer python library. As a last step in the setup, we had to:

- change paths to resources in code, as structure of downloaded data is different than assumed structure in source code
- change names of files in the data/wiki/gt folder, according to source code naming
- insert `encoding='utf-8'` (for read/write operations) or `string.encode('utf-8')` for print statements in multiple places, as some characters from the input files are not compatible with the standard python character set, which resulted in the program crashing.

Computation Li et al. [1] implemented an ensemble of five models, which were trained for six epochs each and the best two were used for the final model. Due to computational restrictions and the need for all data to be used (see *Limitations* for more) we agreed on training only one model for one epoch: approximately 60,000 batches with size 128. This still took us approximately ten hours to run.

Phase two also had a relatively long runtime of 2.5+ hours. Here we used the pre-trained model on the queries that were supplied with the data set (chinaprovinces, countries, disease, sportsleagues, tvchannels, usstates, parties, companies). Even-though the full data set was used for training, the queries of *parties* and *companies* still failed, as required ids were not found in the vocabulary. We were not able to determine the exact cause of the problem. Phase 3 took again approximately 10 hours, and phase 4 similarly to phase 2 around 2 – 3 hours.

¹https://github.com/JohannesKnopp/EXDDS_ProbExpan

²<https://github.com/geekjuruo/ProbExpan>

³<https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1-X4fJSQHgif6WVkv0hGMurMA39fLZx8>

Limitations As stated above (see *Computation*), we were not able to go through all four proposed implementation steps because of computational costs⁴. The first idea to sample the data did not work, as it makes the results incomparable, we need all the data for the queries in the phases two and four and we are still faced with runtime problems. A total run through all steps would take (with our hardware) approximately 300+ hours. This has to be kept in mind while comparing the results and the values and findings should be treated carefully.

Wiki-Data	MAP@10	MAP@20	MAP@50	MAP@100
ProbExpan No-CL	0.781079	0.749363	0.619922	0.548316
ProbExpan + CL	0.784261	0.749062	0.617970	0.545999

Table 2. Average MAP over 5 test runs

Semantic Class	MAP@10	MAP@20	MAP@50	MAP@100
China Provinces	0.890000	0.911561	0.697814	0.686053
Countries	0.790437	0.748466	0.619049	0.378997
Diseases	0.815437	0.874280	0.823456	0.712339
Sports Leagues	0.667103	0.512937	0.227744	0.117141
TV Channels	0.716111	0.492821	0.482023	0.491554
US States	1.000000	0.925274	0.761376	0.716855

Table 3. Phase 2 Model, ProbExpan No-CL

Semantic Class	MAP@10	MAP@20	MAP@50	MAP@100
China Provinces	0.890000	0.911561	0.698310	0.686783
Countries	0.790437	0.745170	0.618036	0.378445
Diseases	0.815437	0.874280	0.823908	0.695653
Sports Leagues	0.667103	0.512937	0.228798	0.117668
TV Channels	0.726825	0.494297	0.479101	0.489124
US States	1.000000	0.921107	0.742971	0.714933

Table 4. Phase 4 Model, ProbExpan + CL

3.3 Testing and Comparison of Results

See Table 3 for results after phase two, and Table 4 for results after the final phase four. Table 2 shows the overall averaged results on the queries for *PropExpan* with and without CL. Generally speaking (and with the above mentioned limitations in mind) the values are quite similar and we cannot see an obvious improvement when using CL. Testing these results for statistical significance was not possible, due to the computational limitations and the nature of the experiment.

⁴Also trying to run it using Google Collab did not help to obtain results significantly faster

4 CONCLUSION

Li et al. [1] propose a new method for Entity Set Expansion (ESE) that addresses the challenge of handling hard negative entities. The method involves refining entity representation using an entity-level masked language model with contrastive learning, and then expanding entities using the improved representation through the ProbExpan framework.

The work the authors have done is generally well documented and includes the code and refers to data sets used in previous papers. However we encountered a few challenges while trying to reproduce their work. Namely, a few inconsistent file and folder references, or missing encoding information which caused crashes. Further, though data sources were mentioned and described in the paper not all of it was easily accessible or no processing pipeline was provided or outlined to handle raw data.

As mentioned already, due to computational restrictions, the results, the values and findings should be treated carefully. We focused on the the Wiki data and found that while using CL, the MAP does not improve, but statistical significance testing was not possible to fortify these results. Reasons for our results are likely due to the enormous amount of computational power that would be needed to accurately reproduce the original paper.

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